
COMBINATORIAL FORMULAS FOR ARITHMETIC DENSITY

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Received: 3/16/22, Accepted: 6/21/22, Published: 7/8/22

Abstract

Let d_S denote the arithmetic density of a subset $S \subseteq \mathbb{N}$. We derive a power series in $q \in \mathbb{C}$, $|q| < 1$, with coefficients related to integer partitions and integer compositions, that yields $1/d_S$ in the limit as $q \rightarrow 1$ radially.

1. Introduction and Statement of Results

In recent works [10, 11], Ono, Wagner, and the first author use methods from partition theory to prove q -series formulas for the arithmetic density d_S of a subset S of natural numbers \mathbb{N} :

$$d_S := \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\#\{n \in S : n \leq N\}}{N}. \quad (1)$$

In this paper, we prove a combinatorial limiting formula for the reciprocal value $1/d_S$, using ideas related to both partitions and integer compositions.

Let \mathcal{P} denote the set of *integer partitions*, unordered finite sums of natural numbers (see, e.g., [1]), including the empty partition $\emptyset \in \mathcal{P}$. Let $S \subseteq \mathbb{N}$, and let \mathcal{P}_S denote the set of partitions whose parts lie in the subset S . For $\lambda \in \mathcal{P}$, let $|\lambda|$ denote the *size* of the partition (sum of parts), let $\ell(\lambda)$ denote the *length* (number of parts), and let $m_i = m_i(\lambda)$ denote the *multiplicity* (frequency) of i as a part of partition λ . Note that $|\emptyset| = \ell(\emptyset) = 0$.

Define the sum $C_S(n)$ over partitions $\lambda \in \mathcal{P}_S$ with size at most n , noting $m_i(\lambda) = 0$ if $i \notin S$, by

$$C_S(n) := \sum_{\substack{\lambda \in \mathcal{P}_S \\ 0 \leq |\lambda| \leq n}} \frac{(-1)^{\ell(\lambda)} \ell(\lambda)!}{m_1! m_2! m_3! \cdots m_n!}. \quad (2)$$

Sums over partitions have a history dating back to work of MacMahon [9, p. 61ff.] and Fine [4, §22]. They are important in modern number theory; the q -bracket of Bloch–Okounkov [3, 14] is an operator from statistical physics that induces modularity in partition-theoretic q -series.

Equation (2) has a natural combinatorial interpretation in terms of *integer compositions*, which are ordered finite sums of natural numbers (see, e.g., [8, Section IV]). Let \mathcal{C} denote the set of all integer compositions. We will extend the partition terms and notations defined above to compositions, with the same meanings. Let \mathcal{C}_S denote the compositions whose parts lie in $S \subseteq \mathbb{N}$. For each partition λ in (2), $\ell(\lambda)!/m_1!m_2!m_3!\cdots$ counts the multiset permutations of the parts of λ , i.e., all compositions $\gamma \in \mathcal{C}_S$ having the same parts as λ .

Proposition 1. $C_S(n)$ counts the number of compositions γ in \mathcal{C}_S of even length, minus those of odd length, having sizes between 0 and n inclusive:

$$C_S(n) = \sum_{\substack{\gamma \in \mathcal{C}_S \\ 0 \leq |\gamma| \leq n}} (-1)^{\ell(\gamma)}.$$

Let $F_S(q) := \sum_{n \geq 0} C_S(n)q^n$ with domain of convergence depending on $S \subseteq \mathbb{N}$; and define the auxiliary series $f_S(q) := 1 + \sum_{n \in S} q^n, |q| < 1$. Our focus is on the behavior of $F_S(q)$ as $q \rightarrow 1$.

Theorem 1. Let $S \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ such that $d_S > 0$, and such that $f_S(q) = 1 + \sum_{n \in S} q^n$ is analytic and has no zeros on $\{q \in \mathbb{C} : |q| < 1\}$. Then as $q \rightarrow 1$ radially, we have

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} F_S(q) = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_S(n)q^n = \frac{1}{d_S}.$$

Theorem 1 has something of an analytic converse.

Theorem 2. Let $S \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ such that $F_S(q) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_S(n)q^n$ is analytic and has no zeros on $\{q \in \mathbb{C} : |q| < 1\}$, and such that $\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} F_S(q) = L$ exists as $q \rightarrow 1$ radially. If the limit L is infinite, then $d_S = 0$. If $L \geq 1$ is finite, then $d_S = 1/L$. The case $L < 1$ cannot occur.

We postpone proofs until Section 2. Here is an example that uses Theorem 1.

Example 1. For $t, r \in \mathbb{N}$, with $r \leq t$, let $S_{r,t}$ denote the set of positive integers congruent to r modulo t . Then as $q \rightarrow 1$ radially, we have

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_{S_{r,t}}(n)q^n = t.$$

We confirm that $d_{S_{r,t}} = 1/t > 0$. Moreover, since $f_{S_{r,t}}(q) = 1 + \sum_{n \in S_{r,t}} q^n = 1 + \sum_{n \geq 0} q^{r+nt} = (1 + q^r - q^t)/(1 - q^t)$ is analytic on $|q| < 1$ with no zeros in

the unit disk, then the series satisfies the analytic conditions in Theorem 1. The right-hand side gives $1/d_{S_r,t} = t$. Note that this limit can be seen directly, as $\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} (1 - q)(1 + q^r - q^t)/(1 - q^t) = 1/t$ by L'Hôpital's rule.

2. Proofs of Theorem 1 and Theorem 2

We prove the theorems using the multinomial theorem, geometric series and the Cauchy product formula for power series, together with a theorem of Frobenius [5]. Our central lemma expresses the coefficients of the reciprocal of a power series as a sum over partitions.

Lemma 1. *For $a_i \in \mathbb{C}, a_0 \neq 0$, let $f(q) := \sum_{n \geq 0} a_n q^n$ be analytic on $\{q \in \mathbb{C} : |q| < 1\}$. Then on the domain of analyticity of $\phi(q) := 1/f(q)$ we have*

$$\phi(q) = \frac{1}{f(q)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} c_n q^n, \quad \text{where } c_n = \sum_{\substack{\lambda \in \mathcal{P} \\ |\lambda|=n}} \frac{(-1)^{\ell(\lambda)} \ell(\lambda)! a_1^{m_1} a_2^{m_2} a_3^{m_3} \cdots a_n^{m_n}}{a_0^{\ell(\lambda)+1} m_1! m_2! m_3! \cdots m_n!}.$$

Proof. The result is equivalent to [12, Thm. 3.1], which is proved using the Maclaurin expansion $\phi(q) = 1/f(q) = \sum_{n \geq 0} \phi^{(n)}(0)q^n/n! = \sum_{n \geq 0} c_n q^n$. For completeness, we give a self-contained proof of the identity for c_n . Begin with the *multinomial theorem* (see, e.g., [7]), written as a sum over partitions λ with *largest part* $\text{lg}(\lambda)$ at most k , and length exactly r :

$$(x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + \cdots + x_k)^r = r! \sum_{\substack{0 \leq \text{lg}(\lambda) \leq k \\ \ell(\lambda)=r}} \frac{x_1^{m_1} x_2^{m_2} x_3^{m_3} \cdots x_k^{m_k}}{m_1! m_2! m_3! \cdots m_k!}. \tag{3}$$

Make the substitution $x_i = \frac{a_i}{a_0} q^i$ with a_i as in Lemma 1. We now let k tend to infinity; if $g(q) := \frac{a_1}{a_0} q + \frac{a_2}{a_0} q^2 + \frac{a_3}{a_0} q^3 + \cdots = a_0^{-1} f(q) - 1$ converges absolutely on $|q| < 1$, then (3) becomes

$$(g(q))^r = \frac{r!}{a_0^r} \sum_{\ell(\lambda)=r} q^{|\lambda|} \frac{a_1^{m_1} a_2^{m_2} a_3^{m_3} \cdots}{m_1! m_2! m_3! \cdots}. \tag{4}$$

For $q \in \mathbb{C}$ such that $|g(q)| < 1$, multiplying both sides of (4) by $(-1)^r$ and summing over $r \geq 0$ gives an infinite geometric series on the left, and a sum over all partitions on the right:

$$\frac{1}{1 + g(q)} = \frac{a_0}{f(q)} = \sum_{\lambda \in \mathcal{P}} q^{|\lambda|} \frac{(-1)^{\ell(\lambda)} \ell(\lambda)! a_1^{m_1} a_2^{m_2} a_3^{m_3} \cdots}{a_0^{\ell(\lambda)} m_1! m_2! m_3! \cdots}. \tag{5}$$

Dividing through by a_0 , then collecting coefficients of q^n on the right-hand side to write $1/f(q) = \sum_{n \geq 0} c_n q^n$, proves the identity for c_n . While the geometric

series representation of $a_0/f(q)$ is only valid when $|g(q)| < 1$, the formula for $c_n = \phi^{(n)}(0)/n!$ holds on the domain of analyticity of $\phi(q) = 1/f(q)$ by uniqueness of the Maclaurin series representation of the analytic function, noting $f(0) \neq 0$ so $1/f(q)$ can be expressed as a power series centered at $q = 0$. \square

Lemma 2. *Let $a_i \in \mathbb{C}, a_0 \neq 0$, be such that $f(q) = \sum_{n \geq 0} a_n q^n$ is analytic and has no zeros on $\{q \in \mathbb{C} : |q| < 1\}$. Define c_n as in Lemma 1. Define $A(n) := \sum_{i=0}^n a_i$, $C(n) := \sum_{i=0}^n c_i$, and let $A := \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} A(n)/n$ if the limit exists. Then if $A \neq 0$, as $q \rightarrow 1$ radially we have that*

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C(n)q^n = \frac{1}{A}.$$

Proof. This lemma can be obtained as a special case of the first asymptotic formula in [6]; for completeness, we prove it directly. For the claimed limit to exist as $q \rightarrow 1$, we need the Maclaurin series for $\phi(q) = 1/f(q)$ convergent on the unit disk $|q| < 1$. Take $\varepsilon > 0$ and suppose that $f(q_0) = 0$ for some q_0 with $|q_0| < 1 - \varepsilon$. Then $\phi(q_0) = 1/f(q_0)$ represents a pole, so the series $\phi(q)$ has radius of convergence $\leq 1 - \varepsilon$ and the limit as $q \rightarrow 1$ does not exist. Hence the conditions on the domain and zeros are necessary. That this limit is equal to $1/A$ follows from [5], which proves when $q \rightarrow 1$ radially from within the unit disk¹ that

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} (1 - q)f(q) = A. \tag{6}$$

Noting that $1/(1 - q)$, $\phi(q)$, and thus $(1 - q)^{-1}\phi(q)$ are analytic on $|q| < 1$, then Lemma 1 gives

$$\frac{1}{A} = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \frac{1}{1 - q} \sum_{n \geq 0} c_n q^n = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \left(\sum_{n \geq 0} q^n \right) \left(\sum_{n \geq 0} c_n q^n \right) = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \sum_{n \geq 0} C(n)q^n, \tag{7}$$

with $C(n) = \sum_{0 \leq i \leq n} c_i = \sum_{0 \leq i \leq n} 1 \cdot c_i$ due to the Cauchy product formula for power series. \square

Proof of Theorem 1. Set $a_0 = 1$ and for $n \geq 1$, let a_n be the indicator function of $S \subseteq \mathbb{N}$, i.e., $a_n = 1$ if $n \in S$, and $a_n = 0$ if $n \notin S$. Since $1 + \sum_{n \in S} q^n = \sum_{n \geq 0} a_n q^n$ is analytic on $|q| < 1$ by comparison with geometric series, then with the stipulation it has no zeros, $f_S(q)$ satisfies the analytic conditions of Lemmas 1 and 2. Thus, $a_1^{m_1} a_2^{m_2} \dots a_r^{m_r} = 1$ if $\lambda \in \mathcal{P}_S$ and $= 0$ otherwise in the expression for c_n in Lemma 1, which yields $C(n) = C_S(n)$ in Lemma 2. Observing that $A = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} A(n)/n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \#\{i \in S : i \leq n\}/n = d_S$ in Lemma 2 gives the theorem. \square

¹In fact, this limiting result holds if $q \rightarrow 1$ through any path in a Stolz sector of the unit disk (see, e.g., [13]), a region with vertex at $q = 1$ such that $\frac{|1-q|}{1-|q|} \leq M$ for some $M > 0$.

Proof of Theorem 2. Since $F_S(q)$ is analytic with no zeros for $|q| < 1$, we have $\Phi_S(q) := 1/F_S(q)$ is also analytic with no zeros inside the unit disk, and has a unique power series expansion $\Phi_S(q) = \sum_{n \geq 0} d_n q^n$ around the origin. In Theorem 1, $1/F_S(q)$ has the power series expansion $(1 - q) (1 + \sum_{n \in S} q^n) = (1 - q)f_S(q)$, analytic for $|q| < 1$. Then by uniqueness of the power series expansion of $1/F_S(q)$ on its domain of analyticity, $\Phi_S(q) = (1 - q)f_S(q)$ on the unit disk. If L is infinite, then $\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \Phi_S(q) := \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} 1/F_S(q) = 0$ which is equal to d_S by (6). If $L \geq 1$ is finite, then $1/L = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} 1/F_S(q) = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \Phi_S(q) = d_S$, also by (6). If the case $L < 1$ were to occur under these hypotheses, it would mean $1/F_S(q) = (1 - q)f_S(q) \rightarrow 1/L > 1$ as $q \rightarrow 0$. But with all coefficients of $\sum_{n \geq 0} a_n q^n = 1 + \sum_{n \in S} q^n$ being 0 or 1, then by (6), $\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} (1 - q)f_S(q) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} a_n \leq 1$, if the limit exists. Thus $L < 1$ cannot occur. \square

3. Further Remarks

Let $c(n) = 2^{n-1}$ denote the number of compositions of size $n \geq 1$ [8, p. 151], with $c(0) := 1$, and let $c_S(n)$ denote the number of size- n compositions having all parts from $S \subseteq \mathbb{N}$. Considering the results in Section 1, one wonders about the “non-alternating” variant of (2):

$$C_S^+(n) := \sum_{\substack{\lambda \in \mathcal{P}_S \\ 0 \leq |\lambda| \leq n}} \frac{\ell(\lambda)!}{m_1! m_2! m_3! \cdots m_n!} = \sum_{0 \leq j \leq n} c_S(j), \tag{8}$$

the number of compositions $\gamma \in \mathcal{C}_S$ having sizes $0 \leq |\gamma| \leq n$. This is a fairly natural statistic, e.g., for $S = \mathbb{N}$ one has $C_{\mathbb{N}}^+(n) = \sum_{0 \leq j \leq n} c(j) = 1 + (1 + 2 + 2^2 + 2^3 + \cdots + 2^{n-1}) = 2^n$.

What are the analytic properties of the power series $F_S^+(q) := \sum_{n \geq 0} C_S^+(n)q^n$, where $|q| < 1$? Let $g_S(q) := f_S(q) - 1$ with $f_S(q)$ analytic on $|q| < 1$. Similar multinomial, geometric series, Cauchy product and analytic arguments as above, applied to $\sum_{r \geq 0} (g_S(q))^r$, $|g_S(q)| < 1$, prove the generating function formula $\sum_{n \geq 0} c_S(n)q^n = \sum_{\gamma \in \mathcal{C}_S} q^{|\gamma|} = (2 - f_S(q))^{-1} = (1 - g_S(q))^{-1}$ (see, e.g., [2, Thm. 1.1]), for $q \in \mathbb{C}$ such that $|f_S(q)| < 2$. Then by (5), together with the Cauchy product for power series as used in (7) above, we deduce the identity

$$F_S^+(q) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C_S^+(n)q^n = \frac{1}{(1 - q)(2 - f_S(q))}. \tag{9}$$

However, limiting formulas analogous to Theorem 1 do not result in this case, as $F_S^+(q)$ is not analytic on the unit disk. To see this, note that if S is a finite nonempty subset, then $|f_S(q)| \leq 1 + \#S$ when $|q| \leq 1$ since there are $\#S$ terms

of the form q^n , with $f_S(1) = 1 + \#S$ exactly. If S is an infinite subset of \mathbb{N} , then $|f_S(q)| \rightarrow \infty$ as $q \rightarrow 1$. Thus $|f_S(q)| < 2$ for all $|q| < 1$ if and only if the subset S has one element. For a subset S with two or more elements, $F_S^+(q)$ converges on a disk strictly smaller than the unit disk, and $\lim_{q \rightarrow 1} F_S^+(q)$ does not exist.

Remark 1. It is possible to find composition-theoretic limiting formulas in a smaller disk, e.g.,

$$\lim_{q \rightarrow 1/2} \frac{1 - 2q}{1 - q} \sum_{n \in S} c(n)q^n = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1/2} \frac{\sum_{n \in S} c(n)q^n}{\sum_{n \geq 0} c(n)q^n} = d_S. \tag{10}$$

This can be deduced from (6):

$$d_S = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} (1 - q) \sum_{n \in S} q^n = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1/2} (1 - 2q) \sum_{n \in S} (2q)^n = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1/2} \frac{1 - 2q}{1 - q} \sum_{n \in S} 2^{n-1} q^n,$$

noting that $\sum_{n \geq 0} c(n)q^n = 1 + \sum_{n \geq 1} 2^{n-1} q^n = (1 - q)/(1 - 2q)$.

Acknowledgments The authors are thankful to Maurice D. Hendon for advice on convergence of complex power series that strengthened our proofs, and for suggesting the special case of Example 1; to George E. Andrews for noting a useful correction in an earlier draft; and to the editor and anonymous referee for carefully reviewing our work.

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